

Catalytic Combustion and Self-ignition Characteristics of lean Hydrogen-air mixtures in Pt/ γ -Al₂O₃ Micro-Combustors using detailed Chemical Reaction Mechanism

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ABSTRACT

Catalytic combustion and self-ignition characteristics of lean hydrogen-air mixtures in micro-combustors with Pt/ γ -Al₂O₃-coated walls were investigated numerically using elementary heterogeneous (catalytic) and homogeneous (gas-phase) chemical reaction schemes and detailed transport. Simulations indicate that the large thermal inertia of the micro-combustor solid structure leads to slow temperature dynamics, and transient response is dominated by the thermal inertia. The time required to reach steady state decreases with increasing inlet velocity and decreasing wall thermal conductivity. The heat localization in poorly conducting walls leads to fast ignition and shorter steady state time. The steady and transient state behavior of these micro-scale systems is described.

Keywords: micro-combustion; catalytic combustion; self-ignition; chemical reaction mechanism; micro-combustor

INTRODUCTION

Micro-combustors are increasingly studied for the non-catalytic and catalytic portable production of energy and/or heat [1]. The energy produced can be utilized by thermo-electrics to generate electric power or via endothermic reactions, such as steam reforming and ammonia decomposition, to produce hydrogen for fuel cells [2]. Hydrocarbons contain a significantly larger energy density than traditional lithium-ion batteries, rendering possible the production of lighter and/or long-lasting devices for a range of applications, such as cell phones, unmanned compact military aircraft, laptops, and telecommunications [3, 4]. In addition, these devices that are powered by hydrocarbons can be easily refilled by adding fuel, while batteries can require specialized equipment and a lengthy time for recharging. This consideration is especially important for military applications [5, 6].

However, there are some challenges to maintain stable combustion in micro-combustors. The geometry of micro-combustors corresponds to a length scale which is close to quenching distance. The ratio of heat loss to heat generation becomes significant because of high surface area to volume ratio of such combustors. As a result, flammability limits get narrowed down and sometimes it becomes very difficult to stabilize homogeneous flame within the micro-combustor [7, 8]. There are different approaches for improving thermal efficiency and stabilizing flame in micro-combustors, such as catalytic combustion and pre-mixed combustion [9, 10], heat-recirculating [11, 12] and "Swiss roll" [13, 14] combustors. The addition of hydrogen as an additive to methane-air mixture enhances the concentration of certain radicals which in turn increases the blow out limit [15].

Maruta et al. [16] computationally studied the limits to self-sustaining catalytic combustion in a micro-scale channel using a cylindrical tube reactor. They showed that, when the wall boundary condition was adiabatic, the equivalence ratio at the extinction limit monotonically decreased with increasing Reynolds number. In contrast, for non-adiabatic conditions, the

extinction curve exhibited U-shaped dual limit behavior, that is, the extinction limits increased/decreased with decreasing Reynolds number in smaller/larger Reynolds number regions, respectively. The former extinction limit is caused by heat loss through the wall, and the latter is a blow-off-type extinction due to insufficient residence time compared to the chemical timescale. These heat-losses and blow-off-type extinction limits are characterized by small/large surface coverage of Pt(s) and conversely large/small numbers of surface coverage of O(s). Raimondeau et al. [17] performed numerical simulations of methane-air flame propagation in a straight tubular micro-channel with detailed multicomponent transport, gas-phase chemistry, heat loss through the wall, radical recombination at walls, and possible temperature discontinuity at the wall due to lack of thermal accommodation. They found that under certain conditions of preheating and insulation, methane/air flames are able to propagate in micro-channels, providing a possible explanation for recent experimental observation. Furthermore, in very small reactors, radial gradients and temperature discontinuity at the wall are negligible but become significant as the diameter is increased. On the other hand, the near-entrance heat loss and radical quenching at the wall are key issues in controlling flame propagation in micro-channels. Norton and Vlachos [18] conducted two-dimensional CFD (computational fluid dynamics) simulation to study the effects of micro-burner dimensions, conductivity and thickness of wall materials, external heat losses, and operating conditions on combustion characteristics and flame stability. They found that the wall conductivity and thickness are very important as they determine the upstream heat transfer, which is necessary for flame ignition and stability, and the material's integrity by controlling the existence of hot spots. Norton and Vlachos [19] also reported CFD results on the micro-combustion stability of propane-air mixtures to study the effects of wall conductivity, external heat losses, burner dimensions, and operating conditions on combustion

characteristics and the steady-state, self-sustained flame stability. They found that the wall thermal conductivity is vital in determining the flame stability of the system, as the walls are responsible for the majority of the upstream heat transfer as well as the external heat losses. In addition, there exists a range of flow velocities that allow stabilized combustion in micro-burners. Furthermore, the micro-burner dimensions strongly affect thermal stability.

Most current prototypes of micro-combustors depend on exterior heating to generate energy for ignition, and the additional equipment necessary to power the exterior heaters can negate mass advantages of micro-combustors. In this work, the hydrogen self-ignition are investigated numerically in catalytic micro-combustors using elementary heterogeneous and homogeneous chemical reaction schemes and detailed transport. The effect of catalytic chemical kinetics on self-ignition of micro-combustors is delineated. Moreover, for the steady and transient state, a reduced-order reaction model is employed to examine the self-ignition characteristics of hydrogen at micro-scales.

2. Numerical models and simulation approach

2.1. Model geometry and mesh

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the micro-channel geometry.

Table 1 The properties of Pt/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalyst washcoat

Property	Value
catalyst surface site density Γ (mol/cm ²)	2.7×10^{-9}
average pore diameter d_{pore} (m)	2.08×10^{-8}
catalyst porosity ε_{cat}	0.4
catalyst tortuosity τ_{cat}	8.0

A schematic view of the catalytic micro-combustor modeled in this work is shown in Fig. 1. The kinetics module plug-in for FLUENT was employed to simulate the flow of hydrogen-air mixtures in the plane channel of height $H=0.2$ mm, length $L=20.0$ mm, and solid wall thickness $\delta=0.2$ mm. The wall material is refractory ceramics SiC, which thermal conductivity k_s , the emissivity ε , density ρ and specific heat capacity c are 20 W/m·K, 0.8, 3.2×10^3 kg/m³ and 800 J/kg·K, respectively. Inner horizontal surfaces of micro-channel contained Pt/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalyst washcoat. The properties of Pt/ γ -Al₂O₃ supported noble metal catalysts are shown in Table 1. For all scenarios analyzed, the uniform grid size of 0.005 mm was used to mesh the computational domain.

2.2. Chemical kinetics

For gas-phase chemistry, the elementary mechanism of Kim *et al.* [20] with 9 species and 21 reactions is employed. The detailed surface reaction scheme of Deutschmann *et al.* [21] (6 gaseous species, 5 surface species and 14 reactions) describes the oxidation of hydrogen on Pt/ γ -Al₂O₃ with a surface site density $\Gamma = 2.7 \times 10^{-9}$ mol/cm². These reaction mechanisms have been used in the previous study and the comparisons with experimental results are satisfactory [22, 23]. For hydrogen fuel, five surface species (H(s), O(s), OH(s), H₂O(s), Pt(s)) describe the coverage of the surface with adsorbed species. Pt(s) denotes free surface sites which are available for adsorption. The gas-phase chemical

kinetics with CHEMKIN format and heterogeneous chemical kinetics with Surface CHEMKIN are imported into the code.

2.3. Boundary conditions

The incoming flow of hydrogen-air mixtures was fully premixed and have uniform inlet temperature T_{in} of 300 K. At the inlet, a fixed, flat velocity profile is used. This boundary condition fixes the convective component of the flux of species and energy, but the diffusive component depends on the gradient of the computed temperature or species fields. Symmetry boundary conditions are employed at the centerline between the two plates. At the exit, a fixed pressure is specified and far-field conditions are imposed for the rest of the variables. At the interface between the wall and the fluid, no-slip boundary condition are employed. The effects of surface to surface radiation between the inner surfaces of the combustor were considered using the discrete ordinates (DO) model. At the outer surfaces of solid walls, the total heat loss via both natural convection and thermal radiation to the surroundings was considered.

2.3. Computation scheme

The fluid viscosity, specific heat, and thermal conductivity are calculated by a mass-fraction-weighted average of species properties. The species specific heat is calculated using a piecewise polynomial fit of temperature. The fluid density is calculated using the ideal gas law.

The conservation equations were solved implicitly with a two-dimensional segregated solver using an under-relaxation method. The segregated solver first solves the momentum equation, then the continuity equation, and then updates the pressure and mass flow rate. The pressure was discretized using a “Standard” method. The pressure-velocity coupling was discretized using the “PISO” method. The momentum, species, and energy equations were discretized using a second-order upwind approximation.

A mixture-average transport model is adopted for the species diffusion velocity, using the CHEMKIN transport database [24], and the gas-phase and surface reaction rates are evaluated with CHEMKIN [25] and Surface CHEMKIN [26], respectively.

3. micro-scale ignition characteristics of hydrogen

3.1 Steady state behavior

Fig. 2 Temperature along central axis for adiabatic and non-adiabatic micro-combustors at steady state.

Fig. 3 Temperature along interior wall for adiabatic and non-adiabatic micro-combustors at steady state.

Fig. 4 H₂ conversion for adiabatic and non-adiabatic micro-combustors at steady state.

The reaction rate of H₂ micro-combustion on Pt/γ-Al₂O₃ catalyst is very fast. Despite the high diffusivity of hydrogen, the catalytic combustion of hydrogen-air mixtures at micro-scales is diffusion limited [27-32]. In the present work, the incoming hydrogen-air mixtures was fully premixed with the equivalence ratio ϕ of 0.2. The effect of inlet velocity V_i on the temperature along central axis and interior wall as well as the H₂ conversion for adiabatic and non-adiabatic micro-combustors at steady state are shown in Fig. 2-4. The micro-combustion occurs close to the inlet section and only a fraction of micro-combustor length is required to attain complete H₂ conversion, even for higher velocity case. The maximum temperature T_{max} is attained at the beginning of the interior wall, by reason of the surface catalytic reaction. As the inlet velocity V_{in} is increased or heat transfer coefficient h is decreased, The maximum temperature T_{max} on the interior wall increases. In the case of non-adiabatic micro-combustors, the upstream interior wall gets heated up because of the surface catalytic reaction, whereas the net heat loss to the ambience occurs in the downstream section. Therefore, for the moderate to high heat losses case, the direction of heat transfer in micro-combustors is from the solid wall to the gas phase in the upstream section as a result of the surface catalytic reaction, whereas the direction reverses in the downstream section by reason of the heat losses. In adiabatic micro-combustors or at higher inlet velocity (low residence time), the above-mentioned reversal is not observed. The wall thermal conductivity also affects the overall temperature distribution in micro-combustors. For lower wall thermal conductivities, the significant temperature gradients exist as

observed, whereas the interior wall temperature profiles are nearly flat for the highly conducting walls.

3.2 Transient behavior

In the present work, the primary purpose is to analyze the transient response of the micro-combustor. The micro-combustor initially contains only air and starting at ambient conditions of 300 K. The premixed hydrogen-air mixtures is fed starting at the time $t = 0$ and the desired inlet velocity V_{in} (4 m/s) and equivalence ratio ϕ (0.2). In order to ensure the reaction system reaches steady state, numerical simulations are run for enough time. Norton *et al.* [33] numerically investigated the effects of micro-combustor wall conductivity, external heat losses, operating conditions, and micro-combustor dimensions on combustion characteristics and the steady-state, self-sustained flame stability of propane-air mixtures. They found that the wall thermal conductivity is vital in determining the flame stability of the micro-combustor, as the walls are responsible for the majority of the upstream heat transfer as well as the external heat losses. Therefore, the effect of the wall thermal conductivity on the ignition characteristics of propane-air are investigated in this work.

(a) $k_s = 0.5 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$

(b) $k_s = 20 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$

(c) $k_s = 200 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$

Fig. 5 Transient evolution of the central axial temperature profiles in the gas phase for H₂ catalytic ignition for different wall thermal conductivities. ϕ (H₂) = 0.7, u_0 = 2 m/s, h = 20 W/m²·K, and k_s = 20 W/m·K.

(a) k_s = 0.5 W/m·K

(b) k_s = 20 W/m·K

(c) k_s = 200 W/m·K

Fig. 6 Transient evolution of the interior wall temperature profiles on the wall for H₂ catalytic ignition for different wall thermal conductivities. ϕ (H₂) = 0.7, u_0 = 2 m/s, h = 20 W/m²·K, and k_s = 20 W/m·K.

For low (0.5 W/m·K), moderate (20 W/m·K) and high (200 W/m·K) thermal conductivities k_s of wall material, the temporal responses of the central axial and the interior wall temperature profiles from ambient cold-start conditions are shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, respectively. As observed in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, the thermal conductivities k_s of wall material have significant effect on the temperature distribution in the micro-combustors; in the bulk gas (Fig. 5) and the wall (Fig. 6), the large temperature gradients exist in low thermal conductivity walls whereas the temperature profiles are nearly flat for the highly conducting walls. However, the H₂ conversion is not affected by the thermal

conductivities of wall material. In all cases, front-end ignition in micro-combustors is observed and H₂ conversion attain the steady state profile in Fig. 4 in less than 1.0 s. Due to the H₂ conversion profile does not change in micro-combustors for most of the simulation time after about 1.0 s, the above-mentioned behavior is often referred to as pseudo-steady-state. Compared with the diffusion and reaction processes, the large thermal inertia (which is defined as the square root of the product of the material's bulk thermal conductivity and volumetric heat capacity, where the latter is the product of density and specific heat capacity) of the micro-combustor solid structure leads to slow temperature dynamics, and transient response is dominated by the thermal inertia [34-36].

Fig. 7 Outlet temperature in gas phase versus time for different wall thermal conductivities. The symbols represent the time when the micro-combustor reaches steady state.

From the cold-start conditions, the variations of the outlet temperature in gas phase for different wall thermal conductivities are shown in Fig. 7. As observed, the time when the micro-combustor reaches steady state is denoted by symbols in Fig. 7. The symbols time is defined at which the maximum deviation of the outlet temperature is less than 0.5 K from the steady state values. As wall thermal conductivity is increased, the steady state time increases. For low wall thermal conductivity, a high temperature gradient exists on the wall; a high temperature gradient on the wall will make the homogeneous combustion shift upstream and the micro-combustor will have a higher peak temperature [37, 38]. On the contrary, for high wall thermal conductivity, a low temperature gradient on the wall will make the homogeneous combustion shift downstream and the micro-combustor will have a higher outlet temperature (as observed in Fig. 7). For different inlet velocities and wall thermal conductivities, the time taken to reach steady state are shown in Fig. 8. As the inlet velocity is increased, the steady state time decreases due to the maximum wall temperature increase and the net energy supplied. As observed in Fig. 7-8, for micro-combustor with lower wall thermal conductivity, the steady state time is shorter. The reason is that the heat localization in poorly conducting walls leads to fast ignition. At low inlet velocity, the effect of wall thermal conductivity on the steady state time is especially significant; as the inlet velocity is increased, the effect diminishes as a result of the increased convective heat transfer. In general, the catalytic combustion in micro-combustors reaches pseudo-steady state instantaneously; the combustion region is a short zone near the inlet section; and the higher inlet velocities lead to faster transient response.

Fig. 8 The entire time required to reach steady state from initial conditions for different inlet velocities and wall thermal conductivities.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, catalytic combustion and self-ignition characteristics of lean hydrogen-air mixtures were investigated numerically in Pt/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalytic micro-combustors using elementary heterogeneous (catalytic) and homogeneous (gas-phase) chemical reaction schemes and detailed transport. The following conclusions were obtained from this micro-scale combustion characteristics study.

- ❖ Hydrogen conversion reaches the steady state in less than 1.0 s and front-end ignition is observed.
- ❖ Compared with the diffusion and reaction processes, the large thermal inertia of the micro-combustor solid structure leads to slow temperature dynamics, and transient response is dominated by the thermal inertia.
- ❖ The time required to reach steady state decreases with increasing inlet velocity and decreasing wall thermal conductivity.
- ❖ The heat localization in poorly conducting walls leads to fast ignition and shorter steady state time.

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